

COVID^X

COVID EXPONENTIAL PROGRAMME

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D1.3 FINAL ETHICAL AND LEGAL MONITORING REPORT

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Authors	Ronald Strauhs (CIVITTA), José Manuel Laperal (SERMAS), Luis Rodriguez (SERMAS), Elena Arredondo (SERMAS), Carlotta Cattaneo (ICH), Ignacio Martínez (SERMAS), (UPM) Silvia Uribe (UPM), Borja Arroyo (UPM), Sokratis Nifakos (KI)
Reviewers	Rita Campos (F6S), Rocío Paublete (BOS)

Abstract	This deliverable presents the overview of the ethical and legal framework covering the development of OC1 participants and serves as a basis for OC2 participants.
Keywords	Privacy, security, data management, anonymization protocol, Data Privacy Impact Assessment, Committee

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Nature of the deliverable:	REPORT	
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CO	Confidential project and Commission Services	

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Deliverable reflects the continuation of the work started during the first year, in relation to the ethical and legal framework developed to ensure that the relations between the partners of the consortium and the participants of the COVID-X Programme, both in its first and second call, can carry out the activities of this project with the maximum guarantees in terms of protection, security of the information processed and ethical issues.

To this end, the following tools have been developed and used as a reference:

- Information Security Policy: This includes a list of good practices and recommended measures to be implemented in the different organizations participating in this project:
 - Internal audit procedure
 - Information Security Breaches Guide
- Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committee: Formed by the project partners and led by an expert in ethical issues and information security in healthcare environments. It has been the body for consultation, advice and resolution of related conflicts.
- Guidelines to follow-up Open Call participants

At the same time, accompaniment and advice was provided to the participants. This has served to create a culture of protection and security of information and consideration of ethical aspects that is very valuable for all.

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ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-X	COVID eXponential Programme
OC	Open Calls
SS	Single Solutions
TS	Team Solutions
CA	Certification Authority
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment

LIST OF ANNEXES

ANNEX A: COVID-X Guide for Conducting Audits

ANNEX B: COVID-X Audit_ Questionnaire

ANNEX C: COVID-X Information Security Breaches Guide

ANNEX D: COVID-X Non-Disclosure Agreement

1 Introduction

This deliverable follows the guidelines provided in D.1.1 Ethical and legal framework and D.1.2 First Ethical and Legal monitoring report. For that purpose, it complements and reinforces those guidelines to ensure the correct monitoring of the ethical and legal aspects related to the development of the projects approved in the First & Second Open Calls of the COVID-X programme.

Ethics and legal structure were defined in Year 1, and have been implemented and complemented with new ones in the day-to-day activities of Year 2. They are of compulsory knowledge:

- The Information Security Policy (developed in Year 1)
- Guidelines generated by the Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committee (developed in Year 1 & 2).
- The Auditing Procedure (developed in Year 2)
- The Information Security Breaches Guide (developed in Year 2)

The participating SMEs needed advice on these aspects due to the lack of related knowledge, which in no way exempts them from obligatory compliance with the GRPD and the legislation in force at the national level.

The issues common to the development of the COVID-X programme and the particular issues of each of the SMEs are detailed below.

2 Information Security Policy

To reinforce the importance of protecting the information generated during the development of the COVID-X project, reference is made to the Information Security Policy developed during Year 1 and included in D.1.2.

The most important messages are reproduced below:

“The COVID-X project has a high technological content with various information systems that store data and with a variety of tools to manage them. These systems must be managed diligently, taking the appropriate measures to protect them against accidental or deliberate damage that may affect the availability, integrity, confidentiality, intended use and value of the information processed or the services provided. The Information Security Policy orders and specifies the security measures to be taken (technical and organizational), in addition to implementing the different technical security elements that the project incorporates.”

The whole text is in Annex A: COVID-X Information Security Policy of the D1.2 FIRST ETHICAL AND LEGAL MONITORING REPORT.

2.1 Auditing Procedure

The audit of personal data processing is the most effective tool for assessing regulatory compliance. Its performance has several beneficial purposes:

- It responds to the regulatory requirements that demand its existence;
- It identifies possible actions for continuous improvement;
- It prevents penalties and sanctions;
- It prevents weaknesses in the system that could interrupt its operation; and
- It guarantees security and privacy for all agents.

Article 24 of the GDPR establishes the obligation to implement "appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure and demonstrate that the processing complies with the Regulation". These measures have to be selected "taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of the processing, as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity to the rights and freedoms of natural persons". Where necessary, such measures will also be subject to constant review and updating, which is only possible by having an audit process as a reference, such as the one carried out at COVID-X.

The audit process for COVID-X has been developed within the framework of the Information Security Policy, and a guide has been developed, see **ANNEX A: COVID-X Guide for Conducting Audits**.

“In date, December 3, 2021 meeting, the Ethics and Legal Committee establish that the audit process:

- *Covers the entire project life cycle up to the start of the audit.*
- *It is an audit of the process (not the product) and its assets.*
- *Focuses on a number of identified control groups.*
- *It is intended to be formative in nature.*

In the designing of the audit plan, the objective(s) of the audit process is to help to guide its planning and execution to:

- *Identification of opportunities for improvement in the privacy governance system implemented by the company.*
- *Adequacy of the measures implemented*
- *Assessment of the ability of privacy governance members to perform their role*
- *Adequacy of the controls in place*

The audit program includes information and identifies resources to enable audits to be conducted effectively and efficiently within specified time periods. The implementation of the audit program should be monitored and measured, on an ongoing basis, to ensure that its objectives have been achieved.”

It is established that all processing must be reviewed and evaluated in relation to its purposes, scope and context in which it will be deployed or has already been deployed.

COVID-X has conducted a rigorous process based on a series of controls that have allowed a broad, complete and rigorous contrast. These controls have been grouped into legal, organizational and technical aspects.

For the correct application of the audit process, a guide has been drawn up that clearly describes:

- The need for the process
- How to correctly orient the audit approach
- What the scope of the audit should be
- How it should be planned
- The specific controls to be audited
- The analysis and diagnosis of compliance
- Recommended improvement actions

In addition, together with the guide, a questionnaire was prepared, see **ANNEX B_COVID-X Audit_Questionnaire**, which each partner was able to complete by comparing each of the controls with its treatment.

TABLE 1 AUDIT QUESTIONNAIRE

DOMAIN	MEASURE TO AUDIT	DESCRIPTION	EVIDENCE	COMPLIANCE	RISK	PLAN
LEGAL	Legitimation Finality	Legality of the treatments (Art.6)				
		Transparency in the information provided on the treatments (Art.12-13-14)				
		Argumentation / Analysis of the treatments based on legitimate interest				
		Contract Review				
		Consent Review				
		Review of Informative Clauses				
		Privacy footers in emails. Privacy policy on the web				
	User rights	Rights Management Procedure. Information systems of user rights				
		Application forms. Communication channels. Roles involved.				
	Privacy from design	Procedimiento de Privacy By Design y Privacy By Default.				
		Data minimization principles. Data retention policy				
		List of initiatives and privacy evaluation from the design: Evidence of the complaint (Minutes of meetings with the participation of the DPO, requirements, revisions and audits, resolution of queries ...).				
		Evaluate if there are requirements to be able to exercise the blocking and limitation of the processing of personal data from the design				
	Corresponsability	N/A				
	Treatment activities	Review of the record of treatment activities; completeness of the same, adequate and updated description				
		Review of the purpose of the treatments				
		Information system used				
		Review of information retention periods with respect to the retention policy				
		Data accessibility review as appropriate to the treatment in the data cycle process				
	Data processor agreements	Procedure for verifying compliance with the obligations of the data processor				
		Planning of reviews of Data controller				
		Model Contract for data processor with access to personal data				
		Adherence to Certifications or Codes of Conduct, if they exist				
	Risk analyst	Personal data risk management				

O R G A N I Z A T I V E	and Privacy Impact Assessment	Personal Data PIA (Art.35).				
		Model for the PIA's.				
		Analysis of personal data of the entity				
		PIA impact revisions in the existing personal data				
		Review of Queries to Control Authorities, if they exist				
		Assessment of the legal, organizational and technical measures applied to reduce the risks inherent in the processing				
	International transfers	Identification of international transfers. Confirmation of destinations with an adequate level of protection or transfers through adequate guarantees (Art.46): Binding Corporate Rules (Art.47), standard data protection clauses adopted by commission (Art.93), code of conduct (Art.40) or certification (Art.42).				
		Management of requests to the Control Authority if they exist				
	Governance policy	Privacy policy				
		Definition of Roles and Privacy functions. Appointment and dissemination of those responsible for privacy.				
		Internal Privacy Regulations: Privacy policies, procedures, protocols, standards, processes, etc.				
		Communication and publication actions of the Privacy functions, roles involved in the organization, as well as policies and procedures related to the protection of Personal Data.				
Identification of the Main Control Authority. Review of communications to the Control Authority if they exist.						
Codes of Conduct and/or Certifications.						
Binding Corporate Rules.						
Security breach policy and other guides	Personal Data Security breaches Procedure.					
	Impact evaluation of the breaches					
	Dissemination of the Data Protection Breaches procedure in the entity and with data processors					
	Lists of breaches and impact analysis linked to them.					
	Review of the resolution/investigation processes of the breaches					
	Review of notifications of breaches made to the Control Authority (Art.33) and affected (Art.34).					
DPO	Analysis of the need for a DPO or privacy officer and decision made by the entity.					
	DPO appointment certificate if applicable. Entity organization chart, DPO position and reporting level.					
	Internal and external communication channels with the DPO with the CEO.					
	Appointment and dissemination of those responsible for privacy.					
	Analysis of the qualification and sizing of the DPO office					

TECHNICAL	Accountability and training	Maintenance of the necessary records (rights of the interested parties, incidents, access, etc.)				
		Periodic controls of compliance with data protection				
		Training and awareness plan on data protection				
	Anonymization	List of technical and organizational measures linked to risk analysis (PIA)				
	Access control	Evaluate the proper implementation of access control				
	Security measures	List of security measures implemented in COVID-X:				
		o Information encryption				
o High availability systems						
o Others						

Table 2 shows how a control has been evaluated, evidence of compliance has been identified, an assessment of the level of compliance has been made, the level of risk has been identified based on previous compliance, and finally (if applicable) the improvement measure that will reduce the level of risk and its expected date of implementation has been identified.

TABLE 2 EXAMPLE OF AUDIT QUESTIONNAIRE

MEASURE TO AUDIT	DESCRIPTION	EVIDENCE	COMPLIANT	RISK	PLAN
Legitimation, Finality	· Legality of the treatments (Art.6)	- IC signed - Anonymization process (for retrospective studies)	High (91-100%)	Very Low	N/A
	· Transparency in the information provided on the treatments (Art.12-13-14)	- Information in IC - Anonymization certificates	High (91-100%)	N/A	N/A
	· Argumentation / Analysis of the treatments based on legitimate interest	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	· Contract Review	- Ethical committee approved including consents	High (91-100%)	Very Low	N/A
	· Consent Review	- Consents reviewed by an expert in data protection from the E&L Committee	High (91-100%)	Very Low	N/A
	· Review of Informative Clauses	- Consents reviewed by an expert in data protection from the E&L Committee	N/A	N/A	N/A
	· Privacy footers in emails. Privacy policy on the webs	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

Following these guidelines and orientations, each partner from the consortium prepared its internal audit process, with the Ethics and Legal Committee providing support and assistance through training sessions and resolution of queries that each partner encountered during the process.

After the end of the internal audit process, the results were analyzed by the Ethics and Legal Committee, correcting those points that seemed confusing or inadequate with each partner.

As a summary of the results of the process, the following observations can be made:

- In the legal compliance section. Improvements were found related to the signing of processing assignment contracts, creation or improvement of internal procedures or doubts when performing risk analysis.
- In the section on organizational measures. The most frequent improvement was related to roles and responsibilities, as well as protocols for managing security incidents.
- In the technical measures section, each partner identified those points that could be more vulnerable, keeping this diagnosis within their organization for security reasons.

All of them found in the audit an important improvement measure that allowed them to reorient their treatment measures or their internal organization in the most appropriate way to comply with the corresponding legal requirements, not only to the GDPR but also to the existing local legislation in their countries.

2.2 Information Security Breaches Guide

“GDPR compliance requires a mechanism to manage incidents and security breaches.

The Information Security Breaches Guide is a mandatory guide for all project partners, which will serve to guide actions in the event of an incident, in an organized way, thereby reducing the time of exposure to risk and the impact on the privacy of the affected people.

The COVID-X project has a high technological content with various information systems that store data and a variety of tools to manage them. These systems must be managed diligently, taking the appropriate measures to protect them against accidental or deliberate damage that may affect the availability, integrity, confidentiality, intended use and value of the information processed or the services provided. This document orders and specifies the protocol activities to solve incidents, in addition to implementing the different technical security elements that the project incorporates.

The objective of information security is to guarantee the quality of the information and the continued provision of services, acting preventively, supervising the daily activity, and reacting quickly and effectively in incidents.

It is essential to publicize to all staff, both internal and external, who provide their services in the COVID-X Consortium about the organization's security strategy and define the general strategic lines of action to avoid threats and react to incidents of security.

The Security Policy establishes the basic principles and minimum-security requirements necessary to protect the information as well as the technology used for its processing, establishing the guidelines for the implementation of organizational, technical, and legal measures and defining those responsible for its development, implementation, and management.

The implementation of these measures will be carried out in a preventive, reactive, dynamic way and through detection mechanisms, which always guarantee the preservation of the information, and compliance with the laws in force that affect its use and treatment.

The purpose of this standard is to establish basic principles, classification and responsibilities associated with the analysis and treatment of information security incidents in the scope of action of the COVID-X project.

The concepts of vulnerability and security weakness are also considered in this document, the early diagnosis of incidents and their effective treatment form an important part of the prevention processes that every organization must have.”

The whole text is in ANNEX C: COVID-X Information Security Breaches Guide

3 Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committee

Following the recommendations detailed in D.1.1 Ethical and Legal Framework and as set out in the Information Security Policy, the Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committee has continued its functions during Year 2 to ensure compliance with current regulations related to ethical, legal and information security aspects.

Regular meetings have taken place to deal with the main issues:

03_SEL & SEC Committee (03/12/2021):

- Auditing (proposal for the Consortium partners and OC1 and OC2).
- Development Confidentiality agreements for SMEs and health system professionals, **See ANNEX D: COVID-X Non Disclosure Agreement**
- Definition of KPIs for OC2 related to ethics and legal issues.

04_SEL & SEC Committee (13/04/2022):

- to address all consortium partners' ongoing auditing procedure of GDPR compliance.
- SERMAS was available for bilateral meetings to support.
- SERMAS organised an online seminar on 30-May 16:00 CEST to explain the process and support the OC2 solutions during June and July

05_SEL & SEC Committee (25/05/2022):

- Information Security Policy was upgraded:
 - Audits. Update of the Questionnaires
 - Webinar on Audit procedure for the Third Parties
 - Development of the Information Security Breaches Guide

06_SEL & SEC Committee (17/10/2022):

- Project overview and final recommendations

3.1 Data & Information Procedures Training Activities

As stated in the Information Security Policy, one of the functions of the SEL & SEC Committee is: “To promote training and awareness plans on information security and data protection for all personnel who provide their services in the COVID-X Consortium.”

According to these instructions in Year 2, the following training activities inside COVID-X have taken place:

TABLE 3 TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Trainer	Content	Activity	Date
SERMAS	Ethic and Legal Issues	COVID-X Webinar On boarding Phase	17/12/21
SERMAS	Personal Data: Comply with existing regulations and Anonymization & Ethics procedures	COVID-X Webinar Sprint 1	21/02/22
SERMAS	Audit	COVID-X Webinar Sprint 2	13/06/22

4 Guidelines to follow-up Open Call participants

For the 2st Open Call, 14 solutions were enrolled in the COVID-X Programme: 11 Team Solutions and 3 Single Solutions.

4.1 Anonymization Certificate

The main issue of COVID-X Programme was related with the ingestion of data from the Third Parties into the Sandbox developed by the COVID-X Consortium. Following the guidelines provided in the Information Security Policy and the compliance detailed in D1.1 Ethical and Legal Framework, an Anonymization Certificate was required for all the Third Parties involved in COVID-X Programme.

The Anonymization Certificate guarantees that all the information ingested in the sandbox is fully anonymized: **see the ANNEX-B: COVID-X Anonymization Certificate of the D1.2 FIRST ETHICAL AND LEGAL MONITORING REPORT.**

4.2 Sharing data procedure

Following the GDPR, sharing data between organizations must be a well-orchestrated process in which all the actors must follow the rules. This is why the Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committees of COVID-X elaborated a precise procedure to be taken into consideration by those third parties interested in making use of extra data: **See the ANNEX-C: COVID-X Data sharing Guidelines of the D1.2 FIRST ETHICAL AND LEGAL MONITORING REPORT.**

5 Follow-Up solutions

5.1 Single solutions

The Single solutions in the second COVID-X Programme were accommodated by the Clinical partners of the COVID-X Consortium (KI, ICH). Hence the clinical partners provide datasets or assessments to validate the technological developments of the Single Solutions.

The D1.1 Ethical and legal Framework includes the *Appendix: Anonymization Guide* in which a protocol is recommended for the correct treatment of personal data:

*“To preserve the confidentiality and privacy of the patients whose data will be part of the data sets that will be the object of the COVID-X validation pilots, **it is necessary to carry out a process of anonymization of personal data, in order to eliminate the possibility of persons’ identification.** This is to be achieved by locating the identifiable information included in the datasets that will be provided in the COVID-X Sandbox and applying on them the appropriate anonymization techniques that will minimise the risk of re-identification.”*

*[...]In addition to the legal requirements set out by the GDPR and other regulations on data protection, it is necessary to **carry out a privacy impact assessment before the anonymization process** so that, in addition to detecting privacy risks, we can avoid the use of resources that may be excessive or not necessary for the intended purpose and ensure the use of resources that are necessary to guarantee non-re-identification. This, in addition to implying unnecessary costs, can lead to re-identification risks that could be avoided.*

*The first step of the data privacy impact assessment, or DPIA, is to **conduct a risk analysis of the anonymization process to manage the resulting risks with technical, contractual, organizational or other measures.**”*

FIGURE 1 SINGLE SOLUTIONS (ANONYMIZATION PROTOCOL)

Prior to executing the Anonymization Protocol, ethical considerations of the solutions were considered, and, in most cases, it was a requirement to get the Ethics Approval or notification from an Ethics Committee, which is the final observers of the ethical aspects when clinical studies are ongoing.

In COVID-X Programme, getting Ethics Approval or notification from an Ethics Committee was a requirement in Sprint 1 for all the solutions, both Single and Teams.

5.2 Team solutions

All Team solutions in the COVID-X Programme, as well as the Single solutions followed the procedures set in the Information Security Policy and the recommendations of the Specific Ethical & Legal and Security Committee.

The Team solutions developed their projects in partnership with a Health Care provider, HC. In this relationship, the HC was the data controller and the SME the data processor. Hence, each team solution followed the procedures of the HC in terms of Anonymization and Ethical aspects.

According to chapter 4.1, an Anonymization Certificate was signed by both the HC and the SME participating in the Team Solution and submitted to the COVID-X consortium.

FIGURE 2 TEAM SOLUTIONS (ANONYMIZATION CERTIFICATE)

6 Conclusions

In order to develop the COVID-X programme and guarantee its success, it was necessary to design and implement an internal organization that could guarantee compliance at all times with the ethical and legal aspects required by current European regulations.

The framework for action was defined in D1.1: Ethical and legal framework, which included the Anonymization Guide as an annex.

Now, in this D1.3, the continuation of the work and its practical application in the solutions participating in the OC2 of the COVID-X programme is presented.

In this way, the work carried out by all members of the consortium and the Third Parties selected in OC2 has been supervised during the second year of the COVID-X project.

The Third Parties of OC2 were trained and accompanied to ensure compliance with the current regulations, mainly the GRPD. Additional measures were implemented, such as Internal Audits, which served to make the protection of sensitive information more solid and guarantee that no security breach occurs during the development of a project such as this one, with so many participants, so many technical interactions between all of them and with the main objective of fighting against COVID-19 disease and minimizing its impact on COVID patients.

COVID^X

COVID eXponential Programme

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX A: COVID-X Guide for Conducting Audits

ETHICAL AND LEGAL INFORMATION SECURITY COMMITTEE

GUIDE FOR CONDUCTING AUDITS

Introduction

Whereas the previous regulation established the obligation to audit compliance with specific requirements relating exclusively to the security measures, identified as necessary for the data processing, now, within the framework of a GDPR compliance, the audit process include, both the organization's compliance (with the obligations regarding the risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects) and the compliance with the remaining obligations that require the implementation of legal and organizational measures must be evaluated.

Similarly, the previous regulation established a periodicity of two years for auditing information systems and data processing and storage facilities, now the RGPD does not establish the periodicity of data protection audits, but transfers the obligation to each data controller to assess the risk inherent in the processing activities it performs, so that, according to that level of risk, it implements the most appropriate control measures, including the audit, with the periodicity it considers most appropriate to the risk identified.

Although there is no specific article that establishes this obligation in either the GDPR or the LOPDGDD, the performance of data protection audits is necessary to respond to the principles of proactive responsibility and a measure in itself to mitigate risks.

This can be deduced from Recital 74, which states that "the controller must be obliged to implement timely and effective measures and must be able to demonstrate the compliance of processing activities with this Regulation, including the effectiveness of the measures".

And in Article 24.1 "Taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of processing, as well as the risks of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, the controller shall implement appropriate technical and organizational measures in order to ensure and be able to demonstrate that the processing is in compliance with this Regulation. Such measures shall be reviewed and updated as necessary.

On the other hand, Article 32. of the GDPR establishes the need for "verification and evaluation" of the technical measures implemented by the controller.

In conclusion, in compliance with the principles of proactive responsibility and approach to exposed risks, organizations shall:

- Have implemented the measures necessary to ensure that they comply with data protection regulations.
- Be in a position to demonstrate their compliance with the standard (including the effectiveness of the measures in place).
- Carry out reviews and updates of these measures.

Scope

First of all, it is necessary to determine the scope of the audit, which is a problem that is not always easy to solve.

There are 3 main blocks of aspects that should be evaluated:

a) Legal aspects:

The RGDPD includes a series of measures whose non-compliance could produce to the imposition of sanctions and this without the need for there to be a prior injury to the rights and freedoms of the data subject. These measures, which we will call legal, are the following:

- To treat personal data in accordance with the legitimizing bases established in Article 6 and, where appropriate, 9 of the RGDPD.
- Comply with the duty of transparency towards the data subject under the terms of Article 12 and following of the RGDPD.
- Manage the exercise of data subjects' rights in accordance with Articles 15 to 22 of the GDPR.
- Include data protection by design and by default, as set out in Article 25 in any activity that will involve the processing of personal data.
- Regularize co-responsibility relationships in accordance with the provisions of article 26 of the GDPR.
- To regularize the relationships of data processor - data controller in accordance with Article 28 of the GDPR.
- To have a record of processing activities, in the terms established in article 30, according to which it is established that, in certain cases, the controller and the processor must keep a record of the processing activities carried out.
- Implement measures that allow for the implementation of a notification of a personal data security breach to the supervisory authority and, where appropriate, to the data subjects, under the terms regulated in Articles 33 and 34 of the GDPR. Within this category, it will be very convenient to have internal procedures and internal regulations, as well as to carry out periodic drills that allow for effective control.
- Carry out an impact assessment in the cases provided for in Article 35 and, if necessary, carry out the corresponding prior consultation with the supervisory authority under the terms of Article 36 of the GDPR.
- If applicable, to have a Data Protection Officer, at least in the cases provided for in Article 37.

b) Organizational aspects:

By organizational risk we mean that which directly affects the very structure of the organization and the decision making that guarantees the reduction of the risk of non-compliance in the matter.

Governance mechanisms that allow decisions to be taken at the appropriate level and with sufficient information, and an organizational structure that allows the involvement / participation of all areas of a company in data protection, will determine the success in the degree of compliance with GDPR.

However, this will require starting with proper training of all personnel. The adoption of internal policies and rules for employees, collaborators and suppliers, both general and focused on the functions they perform within the company, will play a decisive role in this objective.

- Some examples of internal policies or rules could be:
- Corporate data protection policies. Privacy governance policies.
- Data protection controls framework.
- Policy on the use of corporate tools, shared resources, etc.
- Internal rules containing the principles and rules applicable to supplier contracting.
- Policy on mobile devices and the use of teleworking.

A periodic general training program for new recruits or customized training based on the tasks performed within the company will boost awareness of this issue and, consequently, proactivity in complying with the standard.

In short, it is a question of achieving a data protection culture as part of the organization's own culture.

b) Technical or security aspects

Although the GDPR advances measures of a technical nature that may be considered appropriate for compliance with the regulation, it is silent on those that guarantee protection and, consequently, compliance with the regulation.

Thus, the measures indicated in the regulatory text are those that guarantee the permanent confidentiality, integrity, availability and resilience of the processing systems and services under the terms of Article 32 of the GDPR.

In any case and in accordance with the principle of accountability, it will be up to the organizations to decide at any given time, depending on the context and the processing activities carried out by the same, the opportunity and appropriateness of the technical measures to be implemented.

Some examples of technical measures:

- Technological controls for information security.
- Measures for business continuity and disaster recovery.
- Measures to protect the use of common tools (e-mail) such as anti-spam or anti-phishing.
- Protection of Web sites.
- Backing up and updating of operating systems.
- Encryption of files.
- Disk encryption.
- Access control systems. Firewalls.
- Tools for analyzing and controlling user activity in sending information to the outside world from the workstation by detecting information leaks.
- Centralized management of passwords, access control and sessions: who accesses, when and to what.
- User management.
- Incident response policies and security breach management.

COVID-X Approach

In date December 3, 2021 meeting, the Ethics and Legal Committee establish that audit process:

- Covers the entire project life cycle up to the start of the audit.
- It is an audit of process (not product) and its assets.
- Focuses on a number of identified control groups.
- It is intended to be formative in nature

In the designing of the audit plan, the objective(s) of the audit process are to help to guide its planning and execution to:

- Identification of opportunities for improvement in the privacy governance system implemented by the company.
- Adequacy of the measures implemented
- Assessment of the ability of privacy governance members to perform their role
- Adequacy of the controls in place

The audit program include information and identify resources to enable audits to be conducted effectively and efficiently within specified time periods.

The implementation of the audit program should be monitored and measured, on an ongoing basis, to ensure that its objectives have been achieved.

Audit plan

The audit program may address several information systems, performed separately or in combination. The extent of an audit program should be based on the size and nature of the audited entity, as well as the nature, functionality, complexity, type of risks and opportunities and the level of maturity of management systems.

Audit activities:

The Project Leader of the Consortium is appointed as the leader of the audit team, and the SERMAS team as technical experts necessary for the audit, who meet the required competencies.

A work schedule is prepared according to the needs of the audit:

- December 2021. Preparation of this Audit Guide
- 1st – 2nd week of January 2022. Distribution of the Audit Guide among the audited parties.
- February-May 2022. Evidence collection.
- June-July 2022. Evidence analysis.
- September-October 2022 and following. Diagnosis and report

Communication plan and initial contact with the auditee. They will receive the instructions for the guide and will have a channel for inquiries at the email jmlaperal@shealt.eu

Objectives of the audit:

- Carry out a global audit to detect breaches that may affect the data managed by the consortium.
- Identify technical or organizational improvement actions

Audit criteria:

- A measure that is not accompanied by evidence will be considered as “not fulfilled”.
- A measure that partially complies will be considered a “non-conformity” and an improvement action
- For all corrective measures, the period in which the entity undertakes to correct it must be indicated

Audit method.

- All entities will receive this guide and some questionnaires to answer
- They will complete the questionnaires within the established period, providing evidence of compliance
- A diagnosis will be made of the information received that will be analyzed by the Ethics and Legal Committee
- Reports will be prepared for each entity that will collect the level of compliance

Risk assessment.

- In the analysis of the information and diagnosis, special attention will be paid to the different risks in relation to the auditee.
- Special consideration will be given to the auditor's recommendations.

What is audited

Functional domains and their control groups for each that will be analyzed in the audit process are indicated below. Each group includes a series of measures that must be answered when applicable.

LEGAL ASPECTS

LAWFULNESS AND TRANSPARENCY

- Lawfulness of processing (Art.6).
- Transparency in the information provided on processing (Art.12-13-14).
- Argumentation/Analysis of processing based on legitimate interest.
- Review of consents.
- Review of Contracts.
- Review of Informative Clauses.
- Privacy footers in e-mails. Privacy policy on websites.

MANAGEMENT OF RIGHTS OF THE INTERESTED PARTIES

- Rights Management Procedure. User rights information systems.
- Application forms. Communication channels. Roles involved.

PRIVACY BY DESIGN AND BY DEFAULT

- Privacy By Design and Privacy By Default procedures.
- Data minimization principles. Data retention policy.
- List of initiatives and evaluation of privacy by design: Evidence of their follow-up (minutes of meetings with the participation of the DPO, requirements, follow-up, resolution of queries...).
- Evaluate whether there are requirements to be able to exercise the blocking and limitation of personal data processing from the design stage.

CO-RESPONSIBILITY (ART.26)

- Review of co-responsibility agreements for processing.
- Review of the point of contact of the data subjects.
- Review of coordination between co-responsible parties for the fulfillment of obligations towards data subjects.
- Review of how the duty of information is addressed (Art.13 and 14).

This domain does not apply to the COVID-X Project

RECORD OF PROCESSING ACTIVITIES

- Review of the register of processing activities; completeness of the same, adequate and updated description of the same.
- Validation questionnaires for the different areas. Purpose of processing.
- Management programs used.
- Review of information retention periods with respect to the retention policy.
- Review of data accessibility as appropriate to the processing in the data cycle.

DATA PROCESSORS

- Procedure for verifying compliance by data processors with their obligations.
- Suitability analysis of data processors.
- Privacy questionnaire/assessment. Planning of reviews of Data Processors.
- Model Contracts for Data Processors with access to personal data.
- Adhesions to Certifications or Codes of Conduct.

RISK ANALYSIS AND IMPACT ASSESSMENT

- Risk Analysis Methodology for personal data.
- Personal Data Impact Assessment Procedures (Art.35).
- Model/Formalization of PIA's.
- Conducting risk analysis of personal data of the entity.
- Review of the Objective Evaluation processes
- Risk Analysis of personal data. Review of existing personal data Impact Assessments.
- Review of Consultations to Control Authorities. Assessment of the legal, organizational and technical measures implemented to reduce the risks inherent to the processing.

INTERNATIONAL TRANSFERS

- Identification of international transfers. Confirmation of destinations with adequate level of protection or transfers by means of adequate guarantees (Art.46): Binding Corporate Rules (Art.47), standard data protection clauses adopted by commission (Art.93), code of conduct (Art.40) or certification (Art.42).
- Management of requests to the Supervisory Authority.

ORGANIZATIVE ASPECTS

PRIVACY GOVERNANCE

- Privacy Policy.
- Definition of privacy roles and functions. Appointment and dissemination of privacy officers.
- Internal privacy regulations: privacy policies, procedures, protocols, standards, processes, etc.
- Communication actions and publication of Privacy functions, roles involved in the organization, as well as policies and procedures related to the protection of Personal Data.
- Identification of the Main Control Authority. Review of communications to the Control Authority. For example, registration of the DPO. Review of inspections, sanctions, queries to the Control Authority, etc.
- Codes of Conduct and/or Certifications.

- Binding Corporate Rules.

NOTIFICATION OF PERSONAL DATA SECURITY BREACHES

- Personal Data Security Breaches Procedure.
- Evaluation of the impact of breaches.
- Dissemination of the Data Protection Breaches procedure within the entity and with data processors.
- Gap lists and impact analysis linked to them.
- Review of breach resolution/investigation processes.
- Review of breach notifications made to the Control Authority (Art.33). and affected parties (Art.34).

DATA PROTECTION OFFICERS (DPO/DPO)

- Analysis of the need for DPO and decision taken by the entity.
- Act of appointment of DPO if applicable. Entity organization chart, DPO position and reporting level.

ACCOUNTABILITY AND TRAINING

- Maintenance of the necessary records (interested parties' rights, incidents, access, etc.).
- Periodic data protection compliance checks.
- Data protection training and awareness-raising plan:
 - Evaluation of completeness, adequacy of data protection contents.
 - Assessment of the training initiatives carried out: type of training (general, specialized by department, etc.): frequency of training (half-yearly, annual): target audiences (identification of critical figures, ET, RT); territorial scope (centralized, distributed, training of trainers).
 - Accreditation of the training carried out and of the attendance to it.

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TECNICAL ASPECTS

SECURITY MEASURES

- List of technical and organizational measures linked to risk analysis (PIA).
- Evaluate their adequate implementation.
- List the security measures implemented:
 - Security authentication systems based, in two-factor: single-use token, biometrics, etc.
 - Encryption of information.
 - Anonymization that prevents the identification of the interested parties.
 - High availability systems.

Analysis

To obtain the overall level of compliance of the organization, we will weight the levels of compliance with each of the identified regulatory requirements, thus obtaining the level of overall compliance.

Once we have calculated the level of compliance, we will be able to detect compliance deficiencies in specific functional domains and design and implement those measures that, with their effectiveness, will make it possible to correct such situations in order to reduce the risk of non-compliance that has been detected.

To this end, we will act on the areas of the organization where the compliance deficiencies we have identified are located, so that the appropriate decisions can be taken to improve the level of compliance.

Low compliance	11%-50% - Nonconformity
Medium compliance	51%-80% - Improvement
High compliance	81%-90% - Conformity
Very High compliance	91%-100% - Conformity

Based on the level of compliance described in the previous section, we will focus on the audited domains where we have obtained a % of compliance of less than 50%, since everything below that level should be a high priority recommendation in terms of the need to act to improve that level of compliance.

Anything that is between 50 and 80% compliance and that represents medium compliance should be treated as a recommendation with medium priority, leaving as suggestions for improvement and possible best practices those controls that, due to their implementation and effectiveness, comply with more than 80% of the samples or of the audited domain.

When analyzing the results, we must categorize and order based on the priority in the implementation of the improvement actions in the recommendations report. To grade the priority of the recommendation we must take into account whether in those results of the audit tests and controls, there are some of the following ten variables:

1. Age since. Was that control weakness already detected in past data protection audits (here we recommend always requesting the latest audit report) or in the GDPR Adaptation plan and it has not yet been remedied?
2. Large-scale processing: Would the processing where this control weakness occurs be typified as large-scale processing (see definition of large-scale processing in WP 248 opinion WP 248 of WG29 on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPA), which in turn refers to WP 243 opinion, or recital 91 GDPR)?
3. Graduation of the sanction What type of infringement can this non-compliance entail (see Art. 83.2 of the GDPR), the determining factors being the number affected, type of data

affected, duration of non-compliance, intentionality, profit obtained thereby, previous infringements or effective sanctions for the same reason, formal complaints received via the Patient Protection Ombudsman, etc.?

4. Vulnerable groups Is non-compliance with these controls affecting the data of minors (14 years old according to LOPDGDD) or groups at risk of social exclusion (disabled, elderly, children under guardianship, immigrants, unemployed, victims of gender violence, etc.)?
5. Typified as prohibited Is it directly prohibited by the RGPD or the LOPDGDD (e.g. criminal record databases, profiling that results in discrimination of natural persons based on special categories of personal data, etc.)?
6. Purpose of processing Has the data been used for a purpose manifestly different from the one informed to the data subject?
7. No DPO or similar function Has the senior management of that company not appointed a Data Protection Officer (internal or external) or has no function related to control, quality, security, audit to help ensure that the improvement actions identified are implemented and followed up?
8. Lack of Transparency Is it observed that there is an intentional lack of transparency, obstruction or repeated omission to the exercise of the rights of the interested party? Or worse, if the auditor has been observed obstructing the performance of the necessary tests during the course of the audit in order to obtain more information on the finding.
9. Disregard of prior advice from the DPO or the Supervisory Authority Is it shown that the Senior Management has disregarded the advice given by the Data Protection Officer regarding the non-compliance, or worse, is there non-compliance with resolutions previously issued by the supervisory authorities to that company?
10. Data protection breaches linked to non-compliance: Are there already declared privacy breaches and recorded security incidents resulting from such non-compliance?

If the non-compliance due to poor control design or ineffective implementation in the PARTNER or THIRD PART is very low or low and some of the listed variables converge, it will imply a recommendation with a very high priority and even critical (to the point of not being able to continue the audit until an improvement action is proposed and implemented).

We must also consider these other variables in order to prioritize more levels of compliance that remain in medium and even high status, because the failure to carry out these improvement actions may imply that the result of the audit deteriorates and that in the successive audits that are carried out, where before there was an average compliance, it may then be classified as low due to the age/duration factor of the non-compliance.

Audit protocol in the COVID-X Project

QUESTIONNAIRE

DOMAIN	AUDITED MEASURE	DESCRIPTION	EVIDENCE	EVALUATION	RISK	DEADLINES REMEDIATION
LEGAL	Legitimacy		IQ signed	Very high (91-100%)	Very high	N/A

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ANNEX B: COVID-X Audit_Questionnaire

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AUDIT QUESTIONNAIRE FOR: XXXXXXXX

DOMAIN	MEASURE TO AUDIT	DESCRIPTION	EVIDENCE	COMPLIANCE	RISK	PLAN
LEGAL	Legitimation Finality	· Legality of the treatments (Art.6)				
		· Transparency in the information provided on the treatments (Art.12-13-14)				
		· Argumentation / Analysis of the treatments based on legitimate interest				
		· Contract Review				
		· Consent Review				
		· Review of Informative Clauses				
	User rights	· Privacy footers in emails. Privacy policy on the webs				
		· Rights Management Procedure. Information systems of user rights				
	Privacy from design	· Application forms. Communication channels. Roles involved.				
		· Procedimiento de Privacy By Design y Privacy By Default.				
		· Data minimization principles. Data retention policy				
	Corresponsability	· List of initiatives and privacy evaluation from the design: Evidence of the complaint (Minutes of meetings with the participation of the DPO, requirements, revisions and audits, resolution of queries ...).				
		· Evaluate if there are requirements to be able to exercise the blocking and limitation of the processing of personal data from the design				
	Treatment activities	N/A				
		· Review of the record of treatment activities: completeness of the same, adequate and updated description				
		· Review of the purpose of the treatments				
		· Information system used				
		· Review of information retention periods with respect to the retention policy				
	Data processor agreements	· Data accessibility review as appropriate to the treatment in the data cycle process				
		· Procedure for verifying compliance with the obligations of the data processor				
· Planning of reviews of Data controller						
· Model Contract for data processor with access to personal data						
Risk analyst and Privacy Impact Assessment	· Adherence to Certifications or Codes of Conduct, if they exist					
	· Personal data risk management					
	· Personal Data PIA (Art.35).					
	· Model for the PIA's.					
	· Analysis of personal data of the entity					
	· PIA impact revisions in the existind personal data					
	· Review of Queries to Control Authorities, if they exist					
International transfers	· Assessment of the legal, organizational and technical measures applied to reduce the risks inherent in the processing					
	· Identification of international transfers. Confirmation of destinations with an adequate level of protection or transfers through adequate guarantees (Art.46); Binding Corporate Rules (Art.47), standard data protection clauses adopted by commission (Art.93), code of conduct (Art.40) or certification (Art.42).					
	· Management of requests to the Control Authority if they exist					
ORGANIZATIVE	Governance policy	· Privacy policy				
		· Definition of Roles and Privacy functions. Appointment and dissemination of those responsible for privacy.				
		· Internal Privacy Regulations: Privacy policies, procedures, protocols, standards, processes, etc.				
		· Communication and publication actions of the Privacy functions, roles involved in the organization, as well as policies and procedures related to the protection of Personal Data.				
		· Identification of the Main Control Authority. Review of communications to the Control Authority if they exist.				
		· Codes of Conduct and/or Certifications.				
		· Binding Corporate Rules.				
	Security breach policy and other guides	· Personal Data Security breaches Procedure.				
		· Impact evaluation of the breaches				
		· Dissemination of the Data Protection Breaches procedure in the entity and with data processors				
· Lists of breaches and impact analysis linked to them.						
· Review of the resolution/investigation processes of the breaches						
DPO	· Review of notifications of breaches made to the Control Authority (Art.33) and affected (Art.34).					
	· Analysis of the need for a DPO or privacy officer and decision made by the entity.					
	· DPO appointment certificate if applicable. Entity organization chart, DPO position and reporting level.					
	· Internal and external communication channels with the DPO with the CEO.					
Accountability and training	· Appointment and dissemination of those responsible for privacy.					
	· Analysis of the qualification and sizing of the DPO office					
	· Maintenance of the necessary records (rights of the interested parties, incidents, access, etc.)					
TECHNICAL	Anonymization	· Periodic controls of compliance with data protection				
		· Training and awareness plan on data protection				
	Access control	· List of technical and organizational measures linked to risk analysis (PIA)				
		· Evaluate the proper implementation of access controls				
Security measures	· List of security measures implemented in COVID-X:					
	o Information encryption					
	o High availability systems					
		o Others				

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ANNEX C: COVID-X Information Security Breaches Guide

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INFORMATION SECURITY BREACHES GUIDE

Revision: v.0.2

Work Package	WP1
Due date	01/Jul/2022
Submission date	04/Ago/2022
Deliverable lead	SERMAS
Version	0.2
Authors	Jose Manuel Laperal (SERMAS)
Reviewers	Luis Rodriguez-Rodriguez (SERMAS), Elena Arredondo (SERMAS)
Abstract	Internal normative for the correct management of Information Security Incidents and breaches in COVID-X
Keywords	Security, Breaches, Information, Data

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributors
V0.1	14/02/2022	1st version of the template for comments	JM Laperal (SERMAS)
V0.2	04/08/2022	Final version ready to be published	JM Laperal (SERMAS) Elena Arredondo (SERMAS)

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CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential project and Commission Services	

** R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)*
DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

About the EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

GDPR compliance requires a mechanism to manage incidents and security breaches.

This document is a mandatory guide for all project partners, which will serve to guide actions in the event of an incident, in an organized way, thereby reducing the time of exposure to risk and the impact on the privacy of the affected people.

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LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1 - TITLE (SOURCE: PIXABAY)

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TABLE 1 – TITLE

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ABBREVIATIONS

COVID-X	Innovation action supported by the European Commission in the framework of the EC call SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2B
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Accelerate	Transfer technical, business, and ethical knowledge
OC	Open Calls
Single player	<i>See Single Solution</i>
Single Solution (SS)	Open call line for technology providers
Team Solution (TS)	Open call line for clinical partners working in a team with technology providers
AEPD	Spanish Authority for Data Protection
ISC	COVID-X Information Security Committee
CCN	Spanish Center for Cybersecurity
DPO	Data Protection Officer
ENS	National Instructions for Security Normative in Spain
ISP	Information Security Policy
...	...

DEFINITIONS

Security breach: Security incident that affects personal data, and may produce damage to the rights of natural persons whose data is the subject of the treatment.

Cyber incident: Action developed through the use of computer networks or other technical resources, that result in a real or potentially adverse effect on an information system and/or the information it deals with or the services it provides.

Management of [cyber] incidents: All the procedures followed to detect, analyse and limit an incident and respond to it.

Resolution Group: group formed by the heads of the different RTUs involved in the response to security incidents or the treatment of a vulnerability that they value, under the coordination of the cybersecurity UOR, the danger and impact of a complex incident.

Impact: Consequence that the materialization of the threat would entail. Your rating is It is based on the intrinsic characteristics of the type of threat and its behaviour.

Security incident: A single event or a series of events, unexpected or unwanted, that has a significant probability of compromising the organization's operations and of threatening the security of your information.

Vulnerability: A weakness that can be exploited by a threat.

● INTRODUCTION

The COVID-X project has a high technological content with various information systems that store data and with a variety of tools to manage them. These systems must be managed diligently, taking the appropriate measures to protect them against accidental or deliberate damage that may affect the availability, integrity, confidentiality, intended use and value of the information processed or the services provided. This document orders and specifies the protocol activities to solve incidents, in addition to the implementation of the different technical security elements that the project incorporates.

An information security incident is understood as any unexpected or unwanted event that has a significant probability of compromising the operations of an organization and threatening the security of its information.

Information security incidents are normally classified based on their nature and depending on their severity, understanding as such the repercussion or impact that they may have on the organization's activities.

The nature of the incidents, their complexity and their severity determine their classification and also their subsequent treatment. Every organization must define by law how to manage incidents when they occur and the responsibilities associated with their treatment and resolution.

This Information Security Breaches Guide will be integrated into the basic regulations of the COVID-X project and will be disseminated to all participating entities and individuals along with warnings for non-compliance.

1 OBJECTIVE

The objective of information security is to guarantee the quality of the information and the continued provision of services, acting preventively, supervising daily activity, and reacting quickly and effectively in incidents.

It is essential to publicize all staff, both internal and external, who provide their services in the COVID-X Consortium about the organization's security strategy and define the general strategic lines of action to avoid threats and react to incidents of security.

The Security Policy establishes the basic principles and minimum-security requirements necessary to protect the information as well as the technology used for its processing, establishing the guidelines for the implementation of organizational, technical, and legal measures and defines those responsible for its development, implementation, and management.

The implementation of these measures will be carried out in a preventive, reactive, dynamic way and through detection mechanisms, which always guarantee the preservation of the information, and compliance with the laws in force that affect its use and treatment.

The purpose of this standard is to establish basic principles, classification and responsibilities associated with the analysis and treatment of information security incidents in the scope of action of the COVID-X project.

The concepts of vulnerability and security weakness are also taken into account in this document, the early diagnosis of incidents and their effective treatment form an important part of the prevention processes that every organization must have.

2 SCOPE

The scope of this guide is relations with the Security Policy of **all** the Information Systems that the COVID-X Consortium uses, manages, or guards, whether they have been developed within the consortium.

Remember that the COVID-X Consortium Security Policy applies equally to **all consortium partners** and **to participating entities through Open Calls**.

The guidelines contained in this guide and in the Security Policy apply to all employees of the consortium partners and to the companies or people hired by them who participate in the project. Confidential agreements would be recommended signed for all employees.

This Information Security Policy of the COVID-X Consortium will be applicable and mandatory for all the personnel of the COVID-X Consortium or assigned to it who provide services in it; regardless of the form of contracting and relationship with the same, permanently, or eventually, that in the performance of their functions or part of them, develops their work outside their facilities.

It will be the Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee, which is constituted with the approval of this Breaches Information Security Guide, in charge of the custody and dissemination of the approved version of this document.

3 INFORMATION SECURITY INCIDENTS CLASIFICACION

3.1 Classification

The Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee assumes, for incidents related to information security, the same classification and danger criteria defined in the international safety guidelines and standards (CCN, ENISA) for information and communication technologies.

The classification of security incidents will always be established based on their nature and seriousness, understanding as such the repercussion or impact that they may have on the project activities.

A first classification of incidents is as follows:

- Unauthorized access or unauthorized modification of information.
- Loss or theft of data.
- Malicious code infections.
- intrusion attempt
- Intrusion into unauthorized CPD systems, networks and infrastructures
- Denial of Service (DoS) attacks.
- Losses in the availability of information.
- Improper manipulation of physical or logical access devices.
- Blocking of systems and resources.
- Revelation of secrets.
- Software vulnerabilities.

On the other hand, incidents can be classified by their dangerousness or level of severity. That is, depending on its repercussion or impact on the organization's activities.

Therefore, the following levels are assumed internally:

- Low level of danger: the incident is characterized by the limited ability to obtain an appreciable volume of information or to take control of systems (eg spam).
- Medium level of danger: the incident has the capacity to extract an appreciable volume of information and to take control of a system. (eg: exploitation of known vulnerabilities).

- High level of danger: implies an ability to obtain valuable information, as well as to take control of certain systems. (for example disclosure of secrets)
- Critical danger level: it is the highest level of danger, and can compromise the entire organization and third parties. It not only implies the ability to control a large volume of sensitive systems, but to do so in a short time. They are mandatory notification to the control authorities of the local site of COVID-X (for example Advanced Persistent Threat APT)

The Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee considers that an incident is serious when it can be framed, due to its characteristics, within one of the high or very high levels of danger defined above. An incident is considered to be critical when it meets the critical classification.

3.2 Phases of an incident

Incident management phases

Security incident management comprises the set of actions aimed at detecting, analysing, containing the incident, mitigating its effects and recovering the activity of the organization's operations after the impact caused.

The incident management process consists of a series of phases that may be implicit in different stages of the process and will be the following:

- **Preparation:** is the state prior to the security incident. Management responsibilities and procedures are established to guarantee a rapid, effective and adequate response to information security incidents.
- **Identification:** the body itself or a control authority detects an anomaly or unusual activity and generates the notice through the corresponding management channel. An analysis is carried out to verify if the incident has occurred and thus obtain greater detail about it.
- **Containment:** once the incident is confirmed, the objective is to minimize its impact on the organization of the COVID-X project, so as to prevent the spread to other systems or networks and cause a greater impact.
- The information that allows detecting anomalies will be collected and all the partners involved will collect and store all the evidence in a safe way.
- **Mitigation:** After the containment of the incident, measures will be applied to minimize the damage produced in the affected systems.
- **Recovery:** the progress of the restoration is monitored to ensure that the systems or services are restored under normal conditions and the affected business areas can resume their activity.
- **Post-incident actions:** once the incident is resolved, a report is drawn up detailing the characteristics of the security incident, measures applied and results obtained to learn from what happened and that appropriate measures can be taken to avoid a similar situation in the future, in addition to improve procedures.

4 ORGANIZATION OF INCIDENTS MANAGEMENT IN COVID-X PROJECT

The organizational structure in charge of managing information security in the field of information systems of the COVID-X Consortium, will be composed of:

4.1 Common responsibilities

The employees of the partners of the COVID-X Project or the people belonging to companies contracted by them who detect the occurrence of an event that could be typified in any of the groups of incidents indicated in this document must not, in any case, treat by themselves to prove their existence or verify their seriousness, but must report them as soon as possible to the point of contact defined by the Ethical and Legal Committee (by default to the Project Leader), and follow the established response procedure.

Failure to comply with this aspect of the rule may be interpreted as improper use of the Systems or as actions against people or against property; in such a way that legal responsibilities could arise for the person who carried out such verification.

Each partner of the COVID-X Project must keep the information updated for their staff in everything that corresponds to the knowledge, implementation and operational effectiveness of the security controls and incident management that correspond to their area of responsibility. This will entail updating knowledge on legislation, good practices, methodology, technological solutions or market products that allow the necessary risk analysis to be carried out and allow the implementation and subsequent evaluation of measures for its mitigation.

4.2 Responsibilities

The Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee is responsible for aligning all the activities of the COVID-X Consortium in matters of information security and security breaches. In particular:

- It coordinates the activities related to the information and communications systems of the COVID-X Consortium.
- It is responsible for the drafting of the Information Security Policy of the COVID-X Consortium.
- It is responsible for the creation and approval of the rules that emanate from the use of the information systems of the COVID-X Consortium.
- Approves the action procedures regarding the use of information systems.
- It is responsible for ensuring the correct compliance with security measures, in terms of protection of personal data, in accordance with the provisions of the GDPR and local regulations of the different pilots and sites of the partners selected in the Open Calls.

ROLES

The most relevant roles and responsibilities are:

Project Leader, as **president of the Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee**. His/her main function will be to accelerate the decision-making process to resolve critical incidents, defining priorities, establishing the strategy and tactics to follow. He/She must set the main possible crisis scenarios to be taken into account, as well as the relevant technical action and timely institutional communication towards the control authorities of any of the countries of the partners of the COVID-X Project. It will decide, in crisis situations, on the minimum services to be covered, communication with third parties and the declared level of criticality of the incident, the establishment of measures and the distribution of responsibilities.

Technical working groups that are convened to respond to an incident. They will be technical support groups for the Committee in the matters that they entrust to them and, in particular, will be responsible for drafting the report on actions and measures to be adopted after the response to the crisis and the restoration of the service.

Technical partners responsible for the implementation of security measures. The responsibilities will be among others:

- It is in charge of the implementation and maintenance of the security measures on the technological components. Therefore, it is responsible for applying the appropriate

measures to prevent, correct and mitigate the effects of incidents on information and systems.

- Monitor the security status of the system provided by the security event management tools and technical audit mechanisms implemented in the system, under its direct management.
- Inform the E&L Committee of any anomaly, compromise or vulnerability related to security and collaborate in the investigation and resolution of incidents that occur.
- Collaborate in the investigation and resolution of security incidents, from detection to resolution.

Responsible for the Information Security Project (SERMAS partner). Its mission is focused on:

- Advisory, assessment and diagnosis of incidents
- Analyze, together with the E&L Committee, those incidents that affect personal data.
- Advise the most appropriate actions in response to the incident and report to the control authorities.

For **all project participants**. Each partner will manage on its own initiative and autonomously:

- Dissemination and internal implementation of security and data protection awareness and training plans.
- The monitoring of security in its field of competence, the vulnerabilities detected and the security incidents of the information systems of which it will immediately inform the E&L Committee.
- They will actively collaborate in their resolution
- Collect evidence and evidence of security incidents
- Incorporate mandatory clauses related to safety in contracts with suppliers.

5 MANAGING GUIDELINES

5.1 Organization and implementation of the response

The security of information and protection of personal data must compromise all members of the COVID-X Consortium. This document identifies those responsible for ensuring compliance with this Policy and making it known to all members of the administrative organization.

Any person who works within the COVID-X Project, as well as any worker dependent on partner contractor companies, will have the obligation to notify as soon as possible any incident or security weakness of which they are aware that affects the information, services, the systems, the people or the assets of the partners of the Project.

In the case of incidents related to information systems, the channels for notification will be direct communication with the Project Leader, who will immediately call the Information Security Committee to manage the incident.

5.2 Incident Management

This process includes the phases of categorization of systems and services, identification of assets, managers, risk analysis and selection of security measures to be applied, which must be proportional to the risks and be justified. If necessary, a Risk Treatment Plan will be drawn up.

This analysis will be repeated:

- Regularly, at least once a year
- When the systems and / or services provided change.
- When a serious security incident occurs
- When serious vulnerabilities are reported.

The Security Committee will oversee carrying out the mandatory risk analysis. Risk management will allow the maintenance of a controlled environment, minimizing risks to acceptable levels. The

reduction of these levels will be carried out through the deployment of security measures, which will be reassessed and updated periodically, to adapt their effectiveness to the constant evolution of risks and protection systems.

Requirement 12.6.1 k) of ISO 27002 establishes the need to align vulnerability management processes with incident management activities. For this reason, the COVID-X project will follow the same flow of activities for both vulnerabilities and security incident management, at least in its early stages of treatment, with the exception that vulnerability treatment will stop, once the system has been updated or the deficiency detected has been resolved.

The technical partners of the COVID-X project are responsible for the detection of vulnerabilities and will have autonomy for their resolution.

Incident detection is the responsibility of any COVID-X project worker. The groups of workers that intervene in the resolution of the security incident will have the duty to collect and preserve the evidence that is generated during its resolution to contribute it in the instruction of files or reports.

5.3 Low or medium level incidents

This type of incident (low or medium risk) can also be called ordinary security incidents. They are characterized by not requiring the supervision, monitoring or coordination of the Security Committee for their resolution (but it will be mandatory to report it), each partner being autonomous in the detection, diagnosis and resolution of the incident.

5.4 High or critical level incidents

A security incident is high when its level of danger reaches high or very high values (possible service interruption or legal breach), and it is critical when there has been a service stoppage or a proven security breach.

The Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee is responsible for determining, after an assessment, whether an incident can be considered serious or critical and determining the formation of the appropriate working groups to resolve the incident.

After the adoption of the measures aimed at the resolution and closure of the critical incident, the Information Security Committee will prepare a Conclusions Report that will cover, at a minimum:

- The scope or impact on MD activity caused by the incident.
- The determination of its causes.
- The containment mechanisms enabled.
- The people affected (if any).
- The resolution strategy carried out.
- The recommendations to take into account.
- The report on new vulnerabilities detected (if any).
- The assessment of actions to be taken in a new risk analysis.

5.5 Evidences

The Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee will carry out, with the support of the technical working groups, the forensic analysis of serious or critical incidents, and the claim of the evidence that is needed for the instruction of files or reports.

The participants who intervene in the process of managing an incident are obliged to record all the activities they have carried out to resolve them and to gather, preserve and safeguard the necessary evidence for subsequent analysis. The registration and collection of evidence will begin as soon as as soon as the incident is detected.

If legal action is necessary, the Ethical and Legal Information Security Committee will contact the legal services of all partners of the COVID-X Project.

5.6 Information to external entities

It will also be the sole responsibility of the Information Security Committee to report the incident to the control authorities within a period of less than 72 hours, using the tools established by the authorities of each local site. This communication will include:

- Definition and execution of the action plan that determines the scope or impact on the activity
- The proposed containment mechanisms
- The actions aimed at determining its causes, the determination of the assets or persons affected (if any), and the resolution strategy and planning to be carried out.

5.7 Training and awareness

All workers of the COVID-X project and the personnel of supplier companies who are users or participate in some way in the project activity, must know the formal procedure for communication of security incidents and the contact person identified for it, as well as their obligation to report such incidents as soon as possible.

They must also be aware of the types of incidents according to their nature and the action criteria based on their seriousness so that appropriate and timely responses can be offered at the time of detection.

All partners are required to:

- Know and disseminate the information security policy of the COVID-X project.
- Inform its employees and enforce, in their areas of responsibility, the procedures for the management and notification of incidents that affect or may affect the safety of their area of action.

- Know and train their dependent personnel in the technical knowledge and operating procedures that are necessary for the detection of vulnerabilities and incidents in the assets they manage.

5.8 Penalties

In order to offer guarantees for the protection of the information provided by researchers, to generate trust and protection of their interests and those of the consortium, the activities of users will be recorded, retaining the information necessary to monitor, analyse, investigate and document improper or unauthorized activities, allowing the person who acts to be identified at all times.

All partners of the COVID-X project must be aware that their actions may produce legal responsibilities against other partners or third parties if their actions are the cause or have caused a security breach.

All workers of the COVID-X project, as well as external personnel, must be aware of the scope of their personal responsibility for their own actions and omissions in relation to information security incidents, as well as the general responsibilities related to ensuring or protecting information belonging to the Organization and Third parties.

Within the activities of the work package W1, training has been given that includes these issues.

5.9 Auditing and continuous improvement of the incidents management process

The incident management security process implemented must be continually updated and improved. To do this, the criteria and methods recognized in national and international practice related to information technology management will be applied.

The security incidents that occur and the treatment actions that are followed must be recorded. These records will be used for the continuous improvement of the security of the system, and detection of vulnerabilities.

In a process of continuous improvement, the implemented security measures must be periodically re-evaluated and updated, in order to adapt their effectiveness to the constant evolution of risks and technology.

The Information Security Committee will be in charge of starting each continuous improvement cycle, as established in the Information Security Policy.

As has been mentioned, for the development of this activity, the obligation to maintain an updated record of all the activity carried out in the field of security incident management is fundamental.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The indications contained in this document are established as mandatory for all persons participating in the project.

7 REFERENCES

The guidelines of the Security Policy will be developed according to:

- The international standards set forth in ISO / IEC 27001: 2005.
- Information Security Management System and ISO / IEC 27000, if applicable.
- The guidelines of this security policy
- What is established in the GDPR, as well as in the local legislation of each pilot site. For the Spanish pilot site:
 - Royal Decree 3/2010, 8th January, about the Esquema Nacional de Seguridad (National Security Schema)
 - Royal Decree of Law 12/2018, 7th September, about Security of Networks and Information Systems.
 - Royal Decree 43/2021, de 26 de enero, developing the Real Decreto-ley 12/2018, 7th September, about Security of Networks and Information Systems.
 - CCN-STIC Guides of Nacional Security Schema
 - GDPR (UE) 2016/679 of European Parliament, 27th April.
 - Law 3/2018, 5th, about Personal Data an Digital Righths Warranty.
 - About standars of information security:
 - ISO/IEC 27001: Information Security Management Systems.
 - ISO/IEC 27002: Best Practices Code for management of the information information

COVID^X

COVID eXponential Programme

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

ANNEX D: COVID-X Non-Disclosure Agreement

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COMMITMENT OF CONFIDENTIALITY AND DUTY OF SECRET

I. Confidentiality:

1. You are expressly obliged to maintain absolute confidentiality and reserve about the data that you receive for your investigation, especially those of a personal nature, which you may not copy or use for a purpose other than that determined, nor assign to others not even for conservation purposes. This obligation will subsist once the relationship between the parties has ended.
2. The output of information owned by **the Health Care Centre**, obtained from its information systems or from other sources, by any physical or telematic means, is prohibited, unless authorized in writing by the Person in charge of the Treatment of said information.
3. In the event that the relationship with **the Health Care Centre** is terminated, the personal data belonging to it that may be under the control of the undersigned must be destroyed or returned, by the agreed method, as well as any other medium or document in that contains some personal data.
4. Although the data you receive is anonymized, the previous conditions will be equally valid.
5. Likewise, you agree not to try to identify by any means the people whose data you receive anonymized or not, nor to try to undo the anonymization.
6. Any knowledge or information obtained through data analysis must be submitted for approval prior to dissemination.

II. Security politics:

7. The undersigned undertakes to comply with the *Information Security Policy of COVID-X*, and all the instructions, rules and procedures of the Ethical and Legal Comitee of COVID-X, which emanate from the aforementioned Policy, as well as those determined in terms of security for the processing of personal data. For the knowledge of him, he will be provided access to the regulations that apply to him.
8. Logical access to the COVID-X Information and Communications Systems will be done with the corresponding authorization, in the manner indicated and with the security measures that are marked in each case, not being able to access real data without authorization in writing from the Person in Charge of Treatment.
9. If you have any questions that may affect the security of the Information and Communications Systems, you should consult with your contact person or COVID-X Project Officer. The function of the contact will be to offer you advice, attend to any type of query or need, transmit instructions, inform you of its tasks, objectives, among others.

III. Intellectual property:

COVID^X

10. The use of computer programs in the COVID-X information systems without the corresponding license and / or authorization is strictly prohibited. The computer programs owned by **the Health Care Centre** are protected by intellectual property, and therefore their reproduction, modification, assignment or communication without due authorization is strictly prohibited.
11. The use, reproduction, assignment, transformation or public communication of any other type of work or invention protected by intellectual property without due authorization is strictly prohibited.

IV. Right of information:

12. In compliance with current regulations on data protection, you are informed that the personal data provided will be the responsibility of **the Health Care Centre** as Data Controller, whose Data Protection Delegate (DPO) is the **xxxxxxx**, and whose purpose is that contemplated in this document to be signed.
13. The legal basis that legitimizes the treatment of your data is the provision of your consent and your status as a collaborator with **the Health Care Centre**, as well as the other current legislation. For this purpose, your data will be kept for the years necessary to comply with the obligations stipulated in the applicable current regulations. Likewise, you are informed that the data will not be communicated to third parties, except in those cases required by law.
14. You may exercise your rights of access, rectification, deletion, opposition, limitation of treatment and portability, to the extent that they are applicable, through written communication to the **Responsible for Treatment of the Health Care Centre, domiciled at the Health Care Centre to the email address xxxx@xxxxxxxxx**, specifying your request, along with your ID or equivalent document. Likewise, we inform you of the possibility of filing a claim to the National Data Protection Agency (**XXXX address**)

Read and understood, the undersigned undertakes to comply with the requirements indicated above.

Place and date

Name: _____

Signed: _____